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1. *Editor-in-Chief, Impact Surgery*

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Impact Surgery reaches the end of its first year with six successful issues. I'd like to thank all the authors and wider community for marking this earlier milestone. The next step is to attract more research and secure at least size more issues for 2025. Indexing at the end of 2025 is then the major target and will mark the next era. As an open access journal, we will remain free until that point, although costs are increasing. Our metrics are growing and our rejection rate is steadily increasing as more manuscripts are considered.

We have started integrating artificial intelligence into our processes, starting with post review editing. We are building models for initial article screening which will give an early, data driven assessment and point towards the future.

In the supplemental information of this Editorial are two templates for authors to use to submit their own papers. I well formatted paper has a far higher chance of success and far shorter time to acceptance. One is for a research paper and one for conference abstract; please utilise these templates, as they are useful to see how to layout your title page, authorship, abstract, text, references, and tables.